

Presenting Multiple Representations at the Chalkboard: Bansho Analysis of a Japanese Mathematics Classroom

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The widespread interest in lesson study (LS) outside Japan has resulted in the effort to adapt and implement LS in different settings. As one of the key elements in LS, bansho (Japanese board writing) has also gained the attention of educators and researchers. Guided by the representational system framework in mathematics education by Nakahara (1995), this study aimed to investigate how multiple representations are presented as bansho in a Japanese mathematics classroom. Subsequently, the ways these representations are facilitating (or hindering) pupils' understanding were also examined. The findings showed that the abrupt "leap" from a lower abstraction level to a much higher abstraction level of representation could be one of the reasons why pupils were having difficulties in solving the reverse-thinking problem. The absence of representation of relations in the tape diagram could also be a potential reason for pupils' struggles. With concrete evidence based on a bansho analysis, it is hoped that teachers would develop competencies to understand and interpret pupils' learning in a LS context. This effort would be an approach in sustaining LS in Japan, a context where LS is an established practice but might face the risk of being "taken for granted".

Introduction

Inherent to the widespread adoption of lesson study (LS) is the effort to adapt and implement LS in different contexts. Parallel to that is the necessity to make features of LS in its native context explicit because it is claimed that LS is "under-theorised" (Elliott, 2012, p. 114) because it very much a cultural practice in Japan (Kuno, 2011; Makinae, 2010; Sarkar Arani, Fukaya, & Lassegard, 2010). With such long history, it is no exaggeration to say that LS has become an intrinsic part of Japanese educational culture. Consequently, much of the theory behind LS is tacit and implied. In response to this phenomenon, researchers have attempted to provide guidelines and to disclose theories underlying LS to facilitate a better understanding of the LS process.

For instance, Lewis and Hurd (2011) provided an overview of the LS cycle which includes four main stages: (1)study curriculum and formulate goals, (2)plan, (3)conduct research lesson and (4)reflect. Remarkably, one feature that is constantly present during all the stages of LS cycles in Japan is the board writing or, in its Japanese term, *bansho* (Ermeling, 2015). The fact that *bansho* in Japan has survived and accommodated new technologies has attracted much attention from researchers outside Japan. For instance, in *The Teaching Gap*, Stigler and Hiebert (1999) observed that many mathematics teachers in the United States used an overhead projector, whereas almost all teachers in Japan used chalkboard. This might be seen as a trivial difference, but Stigler and Hiebert claimed that "this superficial difference points to a deeper, more significant difference in the way teaching is conducted" (1999, p. 75).

Bansho has always been an essential part of LS because of its importance as a specialist skill and knowledge among educators in Japan. Up to the present, Japanese educators are still constantly honing *bansho* practice and integrating it with current education policies. On the other hand, studies on *bansho* outside Japan demonstrate a tendency to collect shreds of evidence of the effect on *bansho* on teaching and learning, subsequently investing energy to adopt and adapt *bansho* in local contexts. This is essential in ensuring that the decision to adopt *bansho* in a new context is intentional and has been given careful consideration. With that, I believe there is a need to examine the application of *bansho* in an actual classroom and comprehend how *bansho* facilitates pupils' understanding in a mathematics classroom. The findings of the study would create knowledge on teaching and learning that bridge theory and practice in the actual lesson. The development of such knowledge will be essential in sustaining LS in an evidence-based manner.

Statement of the Problem

The concept of representations is widely discussed in mathematics education because it is deemed useful in supporting mathematical thinking (Dufour-Janvier, Bednarz, & Bélanger, 1987). In addition, how representations are dealt with is also acknowledged as one of the key quality aspects of interaction processes in the mathematics classroom (Ainsworth, 2006; Dreher, Kuntze, & Lerman, 2015; Duval, 2006). Pupils' ability to handle representations and to change between representations is considered a core element of mathematical competence because mathematical concepts can only be accessed through representations, therefore making it central for the construction process of the pupils' conceptual understanding (Duval, 2006; Goldin & Shteingold, 2001). Hence, knowledge on how to use different representations merit attention.

One of the essential roles of *bansho* in Japanese classrooms is to visualise and materialise pupils' thinking processes (Tan, Fukaya, & Nozaki, 2018). Particularly in a mathematics classroom, *bansho* is employed primarily to represent mathematical concepts because "writing and the development of representational techniques are indispensable for doing and thinking mathematics" (Greiffenhagen, 2014, p. 505). Nonetheless, exploration of the representations on the chalkboard and their interactions with pupils' understanding is an area that is yet to be studied but is worth explicating. By taking the role of *bansho* in a mathematics classroom in Japan seriously, the process to improve teaching and learning through LS should consider the impact of *bansho* in an actual classroom, particularly how *bansho* can be used to facilitate (or hinder) pupils' understanding. While much research illustrates that multiple representations can be helpful in pupil's learning, it has also been cautioned that "multiple representations may fail to enhance students' learning if they are not used in the 'right' way" (Rau & Matthews, 2017, p. 531). Notably, for representations to be effective, pupils would need to properly interpret each individual representation and make connections among multiple representations. If these conditions are not met, the use of multiple representations may hinder instead of facilitating pupils' learning (ibid). However, some LS in Japan tend to seek "good practice" where teachers are overly concerned with the flow of the lesson more than the analysis and interpretation of the pupils' experiences in a

classroom (Saito, 2012; Sato, 2006). Therefore, to sustain LS in Japan, a more detailed and evidence-based examination that focuses on pupils' learning is necessary. In this study, I focus on a Japanese mathematics classroom where *bansho* is used as the primary means of content visualisation and investigate how the way multiple representations are presented and dealt with could provide more information on pupils' learning processes as well as difficulties.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to investigate how multiple representations are presented as *bansho* in a Japanese mathematics classroom. Subsequently, the ways these representations are facilitating (or hindering) pupils' understanding were also examined.

Research Context

The data site for the study was a classroom in a primary school in Aichi Prefecture, Japan. The topic of the lesson under observation was “What is the hidden number?” with one *hatsumon* (key question for provoking pupils' thinking). The question was presented at the beginning of the lesson, in the form of a *hanashi* (story) as below:

In the beginning, there were 24 children playing. Then their friends came. That makes it 35 people altogether.

Pupils presented their solutions to answer the question “what is the hidden number?”, which involved different methods and representations. These solutions were recorded on the chalkboard by the teacher and by direct pupils' participation where pupils wrote on the chalkboard. The *bansho* at the end of the lesson is as follows:

Figure 1

Actual bansho at the end of the lesson

All the classroom activities and interactions were recorded with two video cameras (one placed at the front of the classroom and one at the back of the classroom) and two audio recorders. The video camera fixed at the back of the classroom was set to record the chalkboard and the process of *bansho* formation. One digital camera was also used to capture photography of pupils' learning materials, and the researcher's field notes were also used as a means of data collection. Particular attention was paid to pupils' utterances and how these were reflected on the chalkboard. Then, the *bansho* formation process (what/how/when pupils' utterances are written on the chalkboard) was reproduced.

Preliminary Findings and Discussions

Guided by the representational system framework in mathematics education by Nakahara (1995), the data analysis showed that there were five representations used on the chalkboard. They include manipulative, illustrative, linguistic, and symbolic representations.

While the abstraction level in Nakahara's representational system increases from realistic→manipulative→illustrative→linguistic→symbolic, the representations on *bansho* did not progress in such order. The teacher started representing the question in an illustrative manner (tape diagram). Then, pupils shared their ways to arrive at the solutions, using a symbolic representation (equations). However, some of the pupils did not agree and were confused with the second equation ($35-24=11$) because the term “altogether” indicates addition. Therefore, the teacher employed the linguistic representation by explaining verbally how the tape diagram corresponds with the equation but without much success. Subsequently, a pupil proposed a different way of representing the solution in a manipulative-illustrative manner. She used her *kanji* grid table (a table with adopted logographic Chinese characters used in the Japanese writing system) to explain her solution to her classmates (see Figure 2). About 5 minutes before the lesson ended, the teacher realised that some of the pupils were still not convinced with the choice of solution ($35-24=11$). Therefore, the teacher decided to employ the manipulative representation of number blocks. From this series of events, it could be inferred that the pupils were trying to “steer” the direction of the lesson to representations of a lower level using *kanji* table grids. When the teacher noticed the pupils' difficulties and struggles, he attempted to return to representations of lower levels as well, using linguistic and manipulative representations to provide more concrete imageries of the concept. The abrupt “leap” from illustrative to symbolic representation could be one of the reasons why pupils were having difficulties in solving the reverse-thinking problem.

Figure 2

Kanji table

In addition, as Hirashima and Kurayama (2011) claimed, in a reverse-thinking problem, learners are required to think about the calculation method only after understanding the story. The sentences in the story were relatively easy, but the pupils were required to consider the relation among them to pose an adequate solution method. In the first representation, the tape diagram (see Figure 2), the teacher tried to depict the relations among the three sentences in the story. However, the tape diagram does not seem to illustrate the transformational relationship (i.e. the “before-after”) in the story. In other words, the sequence

of events in the story which include “in the beginning”, “some friends came”, and “altogether”, were not represented in the tape diagram. The absence of representation of relations among sentences could also be a potential reason for pupils’ struggles. Further examination on this aspect will be performed along with the use of the textbook and pupils’ notebooks.

Figure 3

Tape diagram (translated from Japanese language)

Concluding Thoughts

Representations are often associated with the potential to enhance pupils’ learning. However, it is crucial to determine what and how exactly are the representations facilitating or impeding pupils’ understanding. In this study, a *bansho* analysis of multiple representations has been conducted to comprehend how *bansho* can be used to facilitate (or obstruct) pupils’ understanding in a mathematics classroom. With concrete evidence based on a *bansho* analysis, it is hoped that teachers would develop competencies to understand and interpret pupils’ learning in a LS context. This effort would be an approach in sustaining LS in Japan, a context where LS is stable but where LS could be taken for granted.

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